

Facial emotion recognition based on localized region segmentation

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Abstract: A feedback system for the emotional training of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is being developed. One of the system components is devoted to the recognition of emotions. The use of local regions of interest within an image taken by a web camera during an educative game is tested for Facial Emotion Recognition (FER). The performance of the models were based on statistical data analysis of classification accuracies at each run of the Oulu-CASIA database. Accuracies of up to 98.44% with small dispersion rates were observed. This methodology provides an effective compromise between accuracy and number of extracted feature.

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I. Introduction

Emotion recognition is a topic that has gained significant interest and has shown substantial growth over the past few years [1]. A novel application of emotion training is planned for the treatment of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in children, a developmental brain disorder that impairs social interaction, communication, behaviors and interests of individuals [2]. Estimates reveal that 1 out of 59 individuals are affected by ASD [3] and its “social blindness”. The therapeutic approach incorporates a gaming platform that rewards recognition of emotions in the game scenes as well as adequate individual emotional reactions in response to the game situation. When delivering a certain emotional message, 55 % of its effectiveness is based on the facial component [4]. The game can be individually adjusted to the social competences of the patient. To capture the individual response of the children a facial emotion recognition (FER) system needed to be realized.

Machine Learning techniques are required to transform an image of a face into a corresponding emotion. Feature Extraction (FE) methods are needed to translate the pixel intensities to relevant relations such as shapes or textures. The appearance based FE method of Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) was used [5].

This study utilizes the object detection algorithm of Viola-Jones [6] to extract local regions of interest from images. The classification was performed using 2 classifier models based on K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) approach and 1 model based on Support Vector Machines (SVM). The Oulu-CASIA [7] database is used to evaluate and compare the performance of the different models by analyzing the accuracies of the emotion classifications.

The aim of this study is to show that localized region classification performs just as well as the entire image and

to find a FER model that is suitable to be implemented in a closed loop real time system.

II. Material and methods

The regions extracted were the face, mouth and left eyebrow. The whole face was used as a basis for comparison of this study’s approach. The cascade detection algorithm of Viola-Jones [6] was implemented. The process was combined with different functions for the different regions. The “FrontalFaceLBP” [8] model was used for the Face region. For the Mouth region the “Mouth” [6] model on the bottom half of the Face region was implemented. The “LEFTEyeCART” [8] model was used to find the left eye after which the boundaries of the detected area were altered to fit the Eyebrow region. These functions are located in the Vision Cascade Object Detector toolbox of the MATLAB software [8].

After the correct segmentation of these regions the FE method of HOG was implemented with a cell size of 10x10 pixels, a block size of 2x2 pixels, with 9 number of pixel neighbors, and 9 histogram bins with no signed orientation. The different parameters were tuned to find optimal settings for FE. The HOG data of the mouth and eyebrow were combined to form 1 vector Mouth + Eyebrow, while the face region was taken as generated.

After generating the features 2 different models of KNN and 1 model of SVM were used as classifiers. The first model of KNN was set as EUC1 with K value of 1 nearest neighbor, Euclidean distance function, equal distance weights, exhaustive nearest neighbor search and no standardization of data. The second model of KNN was chosen after performing a hyper parameter optimization function and selecting the highest K value that occurred for both regions, this model was COS7 with K value of 74, Cosine distance function, Squared-Inverse distance weights, exhaustive search and no standardization of data.

The model of SVM was 1vs1 [8], which was based on the Error Correcting Output Code (ECOC) model of 1vs1 approach. The solver of Sequential Minimal Optimization with $1e^{-3}$ as delta gradient tolerance, and iteration limit of $1e^8$ for global minima search was used.

All models were tested on the Oulu-CASIA database and partitioned according to a 70% training and 30% validation set split ratio. Both regions of Face and Mouth + Eyebrow were tested, with 100 iterations for KNN models and 10 iterations for SVM. Each iteration chose a random selection of images from the dataset to be distributed into the training and validation sets. The reduced iterations in the SVM model was due to the low time efficiency of each individual iteration and substantially heavy computational costs.

II.1. Data

The Oulu-CASIA database consists of videos or image sequences from 80 different subjects expressing 6 different emotions of Anger, Disgust, Fear, Happiness, Sadness and Surprise. Each of the image sequences starts with a neutral expression and ends with a strong expression of the particular emotion [7]. The image sequences of the original RGB, of visible light with strong illumination lighting were selected for this study. The dataset selected consisted of 10,379 images in total, each representing facial portraits.

The implemented localized region detection sequence proved to be quite effective. In 10.36% of the images in the chosen Oulu-CASIA database due to missed detection of region of interest processing failed. Those images were excluded from the analysis. The new dataset for modelling was composed of 9,304 images distributed near equally between the emotion classes.

III. Results and discussion

Figure 1: Regions detected for Face, Eyebrow and Mouth. Image of subject from Oulu-CASIA database [7] expressing Happiness.

Fig. 1 represents the different regions detected within an image of a subject from the Oulu-CASIA database. The detection sequence successfully located the region of interest seen in the bounding box and highlighted the importance of region detection by removing background noises that affect emotion classification.

Table 1: Statistical Results from Modelling.

Accuracy %	Mouth + Eyebrow			Face		
	EUC1	COS7	1vs1	EUC1	COS7	1vs1
Mean	98.44 ± 0.26	92.14 ± 0.59	89.56 ± 0.54	98.94 ± 0.21	94.94 ± 0.48	98.84 ± 0.28
Lower 95% CI	98.39 ± 0.23	92.02 ± 0.52	89.17 ± 0.37	98.90 ± 0.19	94.85 ± 0.42	98.64 ± 0.19
Upper 95% CI	98.49 ± 0.30	92.26 ± 0.68	89.95 ± 0.99	98.99 ± 0.25	95.04 ± 0.56	99.04 ± 0.51

Accuracy ± Standard Deviation, all values are in %. CI: Confidence Interval

Table 1 summarizes the prediction results from testing the validation set on the corresponding trained models. The

statistical data shows that the accuracies of the EUC1 model performed the best with greater than 98% mean accuracy for both regions, it also showed the lowest deviations in data distribution. The standard deviations were all below a 0.35% margin for both regions. The COS7 model also performed well, reaching accuracy levels greater than 90% mean accuracy and variations lower than 0.9% for both regions. The One vs. One model showed high accuracies, however with the small amount of generated data a final conclusion was not drawn.

When comparing the approach of region segmentation against other State of the Arts' results on Oulu-CASIA database, this study recorded the highest accuracy with 98.44% when compared to the works of Zhang Huang et al. [9] with 86.25% and Jung et al. [10] with 81.46%. When testing the models against images from subjects not found in the Oulu-CASIA database, the models showed better robustness at emotion classes of Happiness and Surprise.

IV. Conclusions

In this study a new method of localized region selection for FER modelling was proposed. The approach was able to perform well, achieving accuracies of 98.44% for a large database of images. The statistical data validated the hypothesis that the smaller region of Mouth + Eyebrow performed just as well as the larger region of whole Face while using only 12% of the number of features. The region selection methodology provides a unique compromise between accurate results and number of features.

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AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: Informed consent has been obtained from all individuals included in this study. Ethical approval: The research related to human use complies with all the relevant national regulations, institutional policies and was performed in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration, and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

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